

Research

Sex Differentials in Occurrence of Arsenicosis and Its Complications

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Abstract: This cross-sectional study aimed to identify sex differentials in the occurrence of arsenicosis and its complications, with particular reference to women in Aliabad Union of Faridpur Sadar Upazilla of Faridpur, an arsenic-affected district in Bangladesh during November 2019–April 2020. Data were collected from 256 respondents among them 60.9% (n=156) were females and 100 males in age group of less than 30 and more than or above 51 years of age. Most of the respondents (89.8%, n=230) were married, belong to joint family type (74.6%, n=191). Majority of the respondents 41.8% (n=107) had primary level of education and most of the respondents 40.6% (104) family income were into 5–10 thousand. Most of the respondents 44.1% (n=113) were use shallow tube-well and also arsenic removal filter as their current water source. The common features of arsenicosis were identified as melanosis, keratosis and leukomelanosis and Most patients were found in the mild or moderate stage of the disease, Among them only 4.7% (n=12) patients had ankle oedema and 7% (n=18) had ulcer and only 1.2% had Bowens disease as complications of arsenicosis. The female patients were found statistically significant in association with clinical features of arsenicosis melanosis ($\chi^2=21.76$, $P=0.001$) $P<0.05$, keratosis ($\chi^2=40.57$, $P=0.001$) $P<0.05$. The complications of arsenicosis were found statistically significant ($\chi^2=2.24$, $P=0.524$) in association with females ($p<0.05$). It was statistically revealed that females (60.9%) are more sufferer than male. However, there were not found any statistical association between age and arsenicosis.

Key words: Melanosis, Keratosis, Leukomelanosis, Arsenicosis

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Introduction

In Bangladesh arsenic contamination in ground water has been recognized as a principal health problem. The arsenic contamination in the tubewell water was first identified in 1993 in a northern district of Bangladesh. Fifty million people of Bangladesh were estimated to be at risk of exposure to arsenic through consumption of water from contaminated tubewells. Chronic exposure to arsenic causes arsenicosis and may include multi -organ pathologies.(Ahmad, Khan, & Haque, 2018). Chronic arsenic toxicity is affecting more than 150 million individuals in 70 countries that includes Bangladesh , Japan, Mexico, Argentina, and USA (Paul et al., 2013).Drinking water is contaminated with arsenic is one of the major concerns for public health around the world. According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer around 100 million people in the world, including about 13 million in the United States, are chronically exposed to inorganic arsenic (Humans, Organization, & Cancer, 2004; Parvez et al., 2006).The reported clinical manifestations resulting from ingestion of arsenic –contaminated drinking water include pigmentation and keratosis of skin, weakness, conjunctival congestion ,hepatomegaly, portal hypertension ,respiratory system effects, poly neuropathy, solid edema of limbs, and malignant neoplasm (Majumdar, 2018). Arsenicosis is the effect of arsenic poisoning, usually over a long period such as from 5 to 20 years. Drinking arsenic-rich water over a long period results in various health effects including skin problems in which color changes on the skin and hard patches on the palms and soles of the feet and skin cancer (Flanagan, Johnston, & Zheng, 2012).The central nervous system, the heart and blood vessels affected by the arsenicosis and cause a range of internal cancers, specially affecting the bladder and lungs (Hassan, Atkins, & Dunn, 2005).Besides the arsenical skin lesions, arsenic shows its toxic effects by leading to the development of chronic lung diseases that include chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, liver disease etc (Paul et al., 2013).The purpose of the study was to identify sex differentials in occurrence of arsenicosis and its complications.In Bangladesh thousands of peoples are in complications in different area and the complications are also increasing day by day (Hassan et al., 2005; Sarker, 2010). Different studies show that difference in prevalence of arsenicosis in among male and female. In Bangladesh females are most neglected population in accessing health care services among the both male and female populations.

Methods and Materials

This was a cross sectional study. It was conducted in Aliabad Union Faridpur Sadar Upazilla of Faridpur District, Bangladesh. The study was conducted from November 2019 to April 2020. Patients of arsenicosis were the target population of the study. The study place was selected purposively where a total 256 patients were selected also using purposive sampling technique`. Data collection was accomplished by face to face interview with a set questionnaire and check list also filled in interviewing the right respondents. The data were compiled and analyzed by using SPSS 18.

Results:

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by socio-demographic characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age in groups		
Less than 30	46	18.0
31-50 Years	121	47.3
More than 51 Years	89	34.8
Total	256	100.0
Sex		
Male	100	39.1

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age in groups		
Less than 30	46	18.0
31-50 Years	121	47.3
More than 51 Years	89	34.8
Female	156	60.9
Total	256	100.0
Level of education		
Never went to school	104	40.6
Primary	107	41.8
Secondary	37	14.5
Higher secondary	7	2.7
Graduate	1	.4
Total	256	100.0
Occupation		
Housewife	135	52.7
Day labourer	23	9.0
Farmer	49	19.1
Business	30	11.7
Service	3	1.2
Student	15	5.9
Others(Autism)	1	.4
Total	256	100.0

Table 1 summarizes some of the demographic characteristics of the arsenicosis patients. The total study population was 256 among them 18% were in the age group less than 30 years,47.3% in 31-50 years and 34.8% were more than 51 years. 39.1% male and 60.9% were females. In education 41.8% were in primary level. By occupation house wife 52.7%, Farmer 19.1%, 11.7% businessman,9% were daily labor.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by current water source

Above chart showed that most of the respondents (44.1%, n=113) use arsenic removal filter and shallow tubewell colored green as their current source of drinking water, followed by 5.5% (n=14) use supply water, 5.1% (n=13) Rain water & only 1.2% (n=3) from Mixed source.

Clinical features

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by severity of Melanosis, Leukomelanosis, Keratosis

Severity of Signs of Arsenicosis	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Melanosis		
Nil	23	9.0
Mild	201	78.5
Moderate	30	11.7
Severe	2	.8
Total	256	100.0
Leukomelanosis		
Nil	133	52.0
Mild	90	35.2
Moderate	28	10.9
Severe	5	2.0
Total	256	100.0
Keratosis		
Nil	149	58.2
Mild	85	33.2
Moderate	16	6.2
Severe	6	2.3
Total	256	100.0

It was observed that most of the arsenicosis patients (78.5%, n=201) had mild degree of melanosis, 11.7% (n=30) had moderate degree of melanosis with 0.8% patient having severe degree of melanosis. Moreover, 9.0% (n=19) patients had

no features of melanosis. Most of the arsenicosis patients (52.0%, n=133) had no features of leukomelanosis, 35.2% (n=90) had mild degree, 10.9% (n=28) had moderate degree with 2.0% patient having severe degree of leukomelanosis. However (58.2%, n=149) patients had no features of keratosis, 33.2% (n=85) had mild degree, 6.20% (n=16) had moderate degree with 2.3% patient having severe degree of keratosis.

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by complications:

Above chart shows most of the patients 87.1% (n=223) did not show any complication, whereas 7.0% (n=18) patients had shown ulcer, 5%(n=12) had ankle oedema and only 1% n=3 had Bowen’s disease.

Cross-tabulation

Table 5: Distribution of melanosis by sex:

Melanosis	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
No features	17(73.9%)	6(26.1%)	23(100.0%)
Mild	64(31.8%)	137(68.2%)	201(100.0%)
Moderate	18(60.0%)	12(40.0%)	30(100.0%)
Severe	1(50.0%)	1(50.0%)	2(100.0%)
Total	100(39.1%)	156(60.9%)	256(100.0%)

$\chi^2=21.76, P=0.001$

.It was observed that among 100 male patients, 31.8% (n=64) of them had mild and 60.0%(n=18) of them had moderate degree of melanosis followed by 50.0% of them had severe degree of melanosis and 73.9% of them had no features of melanosis. Among 156 female patients 137 of them had mild and 12 of them had moderate degree of melanosis with 6 patients showing no features of melanosis and only 50.0% showing severe degree of melanosis. The severity of the melanosis was found statistically significant association with sex specially with the female (p>0.05).

Table 6: Distribution of keratosis by sex

Keratosis	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Nil	36(24.2%)	113(75.8%)	149(100.0%)
Mild	48(56.5%)	37(43.5%)	85(100.0%)
Moderate	14(87.5%)	2(12.5%)	16(100.0%)
Severe	2(33.3%)	4(66.7%)	6(100.0%)
Total	100(39.1%)	156(60.9%)	256(100.0%)

Chi²=40.57,P=0.001

It was observed that among 100 male patients, 48(56.5%) of them had mild, 14(87.5%) of them had moderate degree of keratosis ,but 36(24.2%) of them did not show any feature of keratosis and 33.3% showing severe degree of keratosis.Among 156 female patients 37(43.5%) of them had mild and 2(12.5%) of them had moderate degree of keratosis with 108 patients showing no features of keratosis and 66.7% showing severe degree of keratosis. The severity of the keratosis was found statistically significant association with sex specially with the female (p<0.05).

Table 7: Distribution of leukomelanosis by sex

Leukomelanosis	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Nil	34(25.6%)	99(74.4%)	133(100.0%)
Mild	45(50.0%)	45(50.0%)	90(100.0%)
Moderate	19(67.9%)	9(32.1%)	28(100.0%)
Severe	2(40.0%)	3(60.0%)	5(100.0%)
Total	100(39.1%)	156(60.9%)	256(100.0%)

Chi²=40.57,P=0.001

It was observed that among 100(39.1%) male patients, 45(50.0%) of them had mild degree of leukomelanosis, 19(67.9) of them had moderate degree of leukomelanosis, but 34(25.6%) of them did not show any features of leukomelanosis with

2(40.0%) showing severe degree of leukomelanosis. Among 156(60.9) female patients, 45(50.0%) of them had mild and 9(32.1%) of them had moderate degree of leukomelanosis with 99(74.4%) patients showing no features of leukomelanosis and 2(40.0%) patients had severe degree of leukomelanosis. The severity of the leukomelanosis was found statistically significant association with sex specially with the female ($p < 0.05$)

Table-8 Distribution of complications of arsenicosis by sex:

Complications	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Nil	84(37.8%)	138(62.2%)	222(100.0%)
Ulcer	10(55.6%)	8(44.4%)	18(100.0%)
Bowen's	1(33.3%)	2(66.7%)	3(100.0%)
Oedema	5(38.5%)	8(61.5%)	13(100.0%)
Total	100(39.1%)	156(60.9%)	256(100.0%)

$\chi^2=2.24$, $P=.524$

It was observed that among 100(39.1%) male patients, 10(55.6%) of them had ulcer, 1(33.3%) of them had Bowen's disease and 5(38.5%) of them had ankle oedema with 84(37.8%) of them had no complications. Among 156(60.9%) female patients' majority of them 138(62.2%) had no complications followed by 44.4% of them had ulcer, 66.7% of them had Bowen's disease and 61.5% of them had ankle oedema. The complications of arsenicosis was found statistically not significant association with sex specially with the female ($p < 0.05$)

Discussion

A cross sectional study was conducted to understand the sex differentials in occurrence of the arsenicosis and its complications. This study was conducted in some highly arsenic affected villages of Bangladesh.

Socio-demographic characteristics:

A total 256 respondents were included in this study of which 60.9% were female arsenicosis patient and 39.1% were male. The mean age of the study population was 45.68 ± 14.091 years ranging from less than 30 to more than 51 years. Out of 256 respondents, majority 47.3% were in the age group of 31- 50 years. By gender most 60.9% of them were female. A Study found that Women exposed to arsenic $>50 \mu\text{g/L}$ were at 1.9 times (Odds Ratio = 1.9, 95% CI = 1.1–3.6) increased risk of malnutrition compared to unexposed. The findings of this study suggest that chronic arsenic exposure is likely to contribute to poor nutritional status among women of 20–45 years (Abul H Milton et al., 2010).

By the level of education, a majority 41.8% of the respondents had primary level education and 40.6% were illiterate. By occupation most of the respondents 52.7% were housewife. By gender among arsenicosis respondents 60.9% were female whereas 39.1% were male. A similar Studies conducted by Khan AW et.al found that male are more sufferer than female by arsenicosis. They found 54% male arsenicosis patient in their study (Khan, 1998).

Study conducted by Milton AH and Rahman M also found more male arsenicosis patient in the ratio of 1.5:1(male: female) (Abul Hasnat Milton & Rahman, 1999). Though in a different study they found 47.4% female patients (Ahmad et al., 1999). In another follow up study done by the same researcher reported that among the study population 62% were male (Tondel et al., 1999). Another Study found that the chronic effect due to arsenic poisoning is about 32% and

the men (69.33%) were more susceptible to arsenicosis. Among the affected patients identified problems were melanosis (94%), keratosis (33%), leucomelanosis (38%) (Sultana, Hossian, & Pervin, 2013).

By the current water source among 256 respondents most of them 44.1% use shallow tube well and arsenic removal filter for drinking, followed by 5.5% supply water, 5.1% rain water and only 1.2% from mixed source.

Clinical Manifestations:

By clinical observation among the total 256 respondents most of the arsenicosis patients (78.5%, n=201) had mild melanosis, whereas 11.7% had moderate degree of melanosis with only 0.8% patients having severe degree of melanosis. While among the 256 arsenicosis patient most of them (52%, n=133) had no features of leukomelanosis, 35.2% had mild degree, 10.9% had moderate degree with only 2% patient having severe degree of leukomelanosis and among 256 respondents 58.2% had no features of keratosis whereas 33.2% had mild degree of keratosis with only 2.3 having severe degree of keratosis. Among the total 256 respondents most of the them (87.1%) did not show any complications, whereas only 7% respondents had shown ulcer, 4.7% shown ankle oedema and only 1.2% had Bowens disease.

Another Study conducted by A. Wadud Khan, Sk. Akhtar Ahmad, M.H. Salim Ullah Sayed, Sk. Abdul Hadi, M.H. Faruque, Manzurul Haque Khan, Md. Abdul Jalil and Rukshana Ahmed found that The most common presentations are melanosis (93.5%), keratosis (68.3%), leukomelanosis (39.1%) and hyperkeratosis (37.6%). A few patients (0.8%) with obvious skin cancers have been detected (Khan & Ahmad, 1997).

Cross-tabulation between sex and clinical feature of Arsenicosis: The current study shows that the severity of melanosis had statistically significant association with sex specially with the female respondents ($\text{Chi}^2=21.76, P=0.001$). Among 256 respondents 39.1 male respondents, 31.8% of them had mild and only 40% of them had moderate degree of melanosis. Among 156 female respondents 68.2% of them had mild and 40% of them had moderate degree of melanosis with 26.1% respondents showing no features of melanosis.

The severity of Leukomelanosis had statistically significant association with sex specially with the female respondents ($\text{Chi}^2=40.57, P=0.001$). Among 256 respondents 100 male respondents, 50% of them had mild and 67.9% of them had moderate degree of leukomelanosis and only 25.6% of them did not show any features of leukomelanosis. Among 156 female respondents 50% of them had mild and 32.1% of them had moderate degree of leukomelanosis with majority of them 74.4% respondents showing no features of leukomelanosis. ($P<0.05$)

The severity of keratosis was found statistically significant in association with sex specially with the female respondents ($\text{Chi}^2=40.57, P=0.001$). Among 256 respondents 100 male respondents 56.5% of them had mild and only 87.5%, (n=14) of them had moderate degree of keratosis and 24.2% of them did not show any features of keratosis. Among 156 female respondents 43.5% of them had mild and 12.5% of them had moderate degree of keratosis with majority of them 75.8% respondents had no features of keratosis. ($P>0.05$) and only 66.7%, (n=4) had severe degree of keratosis.

The complications of Arsenicosis was found statistically significant in association with sex specially with the female respondents ($\text{Chi}^2=2.24, P=0.524$). Among 256 respondents 100 male respondents, 37.8% (n=84) of them had no complications only 55.6%, (n=10) had ulcer and 38.5%, (n=5) had oedema and only 33.3%, (n=1) bowens disease. Among 156 females 62.2% respondents did not show any complication whereas 61.5% (n=8) respondent was found to have ankle oedema, 44.4% (n=8) had ulcer with only 66.7% (n=2) had Bowens disease. ($P>0.05$)

The current study shows that the severity of melanosis was found statistically not significant in association with age specially with the female respondents ($\text{Chi}^2=2.26, P=0.894$). Among 256 respondents maximum 121 patients were found in the age group of 31-50 years, among whose 46.8% of them had mild and 50% (n=15) had moderate degree of melanosis, whereas only 10% respondents were found moderate degree of melanosis in the age group of less than 30 years. ($P>0.05$)

The severity of leukomelanosis was found statistically not significant in association with age specially with the female respondents ($\text{Chi}^2=6.15, P=0.406$). Among 256 respondents maximum 121 patients were found in the age group of 31-50 years, among whose 40% of them had mild and only 42.9% (n=12) had moderate degree of

leukomelanosis, whereas only 10.7% (n=3) respondents were found moderate degree of leukomelanosis in the age group of less than 30 years. (P>0.05)

The severity of keratosis was found statistically not significant in association with age specially with the female respondents (Chi-square/ χ^2 =7.01, P=0.320). Among 256 respondents maximum 121 patients were found in the age group of 31-50 years, among 50.6% (n=43) of them had mild and only 50.0% (n=8) had moderate degree of keratosis.

Whereas only 7% (n=7) respondents was found in the age group of more than or above 51 years of age moderate degree of keratosis. (P>0.05) The complications of Arsenicosis was found statistically not significant in association with age specially with the female respondents (Chi-square/ χ^2 =15.55, P=0.016). Among 256 respondents maximum 121 patients were found in the age group of 31-50 years, among whose 49.5% of them had no complications whereas only 33.3% (n=6) had ulcer, 38.5% (n=5) had oedema. (P>0.05)

Conclusion: Arsenic possess health risks to a significant proportion of the population both male and female, and the numbers of those at risk is likely to grow if effective action is not taken urgently. This current study revealed that females are more vulnerable in occurrence of arsenicosis so more concern should be given on their health & health education, diet & nutrition, economic freedom etc irrespective of their age. However, the complications and the clinical features of arsenicosis was found statistically not significant associated with age specially with the female respondent. A massive awareness could be increases on important of taking arsenic free safe water as well as protein and vitamin rich food specially for the females. More Importance could be given on the health seeking behavior specially for the females. Same study could be conducted with large population to confirm the findings.

References

- [1] Ahmad, S. A., Khan, M. H., & Haque, M. (2018). Arsenic contamination in groundwater in Bangladesh: implications and challenges for healthcare policy. *Risk management and healthcare policy*, 11, 251.
- [2] Ahmad, S. A., Sayed, M. S. U., Hadi, S. A., Faruquee, M., Khan, M. H., Jalil, M. A., . . . Khan, A. W. (1999). Arsenicosis in a village in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Environmental Health Research*, 9(3), 187-195.
- [3] Flanagan, S. V., Johnston, R. B., & Zheng, Y. (2012). Arsenic in tube well water in Bangladesh: health and economic impacts and implications for arsenic mitigation. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 90, 839-846.
- [4] Hassan, M. M., Atkins, P. J., & Dunn, C. E. (2005). Social implications of arsenic poisoning in Bangladesh. *Social Science & Medicine*, 61(10), 2201-2211.
- [5] Humans, I. W. G. o. t. E. o. C. R. t., Organization, W. H., & Cancer, I. A. f. R. o. (2004). *Some drinking-water disinfectants and contaminants, including arsenic* (Vol. 84): IARC.
- [6] Khan, A. W. (1998). *Arsenic contamination in ground water and its effect on human health with particular reference to Bangladesh*. Paper presented at the International Conference on Arsenic Pollution of Groundwater in Bangladesh, 8-12 February 1998.
- [7] Khan, A. W., & Ahmad, S. A. (1997). Arsenic in drinking water: health effects and management. *A Training Manual Department of Occupational and Public Health, National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM), Dhaka*.
- [8] Majumdar, K. K. (2018). Effect of arsenic safe water on manifestations of arsenicosis. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 5(10), 4573.
- [9] Milton, A. H., & Rahman, M. (1999). Environmental pollution and skin involvement pattern of chronic arsenicosis in Bangladesh. *Journal of occupational health*, 41(4), 207-208.
- [10] Milton, A. H., Shahidullah, S., Smith, W., Hossain, K. S., Hasan, Z., & Ahmed, K. T. (2010). Association between chronic arsenic exposure and nutritional status among the women of child bearing age: a case-control study in Bangladesh. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 7(7), 2811-2821.
- [11] Parvez, F., Chen, Y., Argos, M., Hussain, A. I., Momotaj, H., Dhar, R., . . . Ahsan, H. (2006). Prevalence of arsenic exposure from drinking water and awareness of its health risks in a Bangladeshi population: results from a large population-based study. *Environmental health perspectives*, 114(3), 355-359.

- [12] Paul, S., Das, N., Bhattacharjee, P., Banerjee, M., Das, J. K., Sarma, N., . . . Basu, S. (2013). Arsenic-induced toxicity and carcinogenicity: a two-wave cross-sectional study in arsenicosis individuals in West Bengal, India. *Journal of exposure science & environmental epidemiology*, 23(2), 156-162.
- [13] Sarker, M. (2010). Determinants of arsenicosis patients' perception and social implications of arsenic poisoning through groundwater in Bangladesh. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 7(10), 3644-3656.
- [14] Sultana, S., Hossain, Q., & Pervin, R. (2013). Socioeconomic condition and health status of chronic arsenicosis patients in Jessore, Bangladesh. *Int J Advan Nutr & Health Sci*, 1(1), 9.
- [15] Tondel, M., Rahman, M., Magnuson, A., Chowdhury, I. A., Faruquee, M. H., & Ahmad, S. A. (1999). The relationship of arsenic levels in drinking water and the prevalence rate of skin lesions in Bangladesh. *Environmental health perspectives*, 107(9), 727-729.

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